

Pea steak and almond drink: Meat and dairy substitutes on the menu

Abridged version of the TA-SWISS study “Fleisch- und Milchersatzprodukte – besser für Gesundheit und Umwelt? Auswirkungen auf Ernährung und Nachhaltigkeit, die Sicht der Konsumentinnen und Konsumenten sowie ethische und rechtliche Überlegungen”

TA-SWISS, the Foundation for Technology Assessment and a centre for excellence of the Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences, deals with the opportunities and risks of new technologies.

This abridged version is based on a scientific study carried out on behalf of TA-SWISS by an interdisciplinary project team under the leadership of Dr. Mélanie Douziech und Eric Mehner from the Swiss agricultural research center Agroscope. The University of Bern also participated in the study. The abridged version presents the most important results and conclusions of the study in condensed form and is aimed at a broad audience.

Fleisch- und Milchersatzprodukte – besser für Gesundheit und Umwelt? Auswirkungen auf Ernährung und Nachhaltigkeit, die Sicht der Konsumentinnen und Konsumenten sowie ethische und rechtliche Überlegungen

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Meat and dairy substitutes: a brief overview

The foodstuffs sector is offering an increasing selection of plant-based substitutes for dairy products and meat. This is in response to demand from a clientele that due to ecological, animal protection or health considerations wants to consume fewer products of animal origin, or refrain from consuming them altogether.

Opportunities ...

The environmental impacts of the manufacture of alternative meat products – calculated on the basis of water consumption and land use, as well as on CO₂ emissions and loss of biodiversity – are significantly lower in comparison with the production of meat. The benefits associated with the production of plant-based alternatives to dairy products are lower, but they still exist in products such as soya-based drinks.

The consumption of red meat and sausage products in particular can increase the risk of cardiovascular disorders, as well as certain types of cancer and other non-communicable diseases. Thus, meat substitutes offer potential health benefits.

Both meat and dairy substitutes have a positive impact in terms of animal welfare.

A largely plant-based diet can increase Switzerland's degree of self-sufficiency with respect to the supply of foodstuffs.

... Risks ...

Vitamin B12, which is essential for the functioning of the nervous system, as well as for various metabolic processes and blood formation, is only found in animal-based products. Human beings are less able to absorb other essential micronutrients such as iron if these are of plant-based origin. An exclusively plant-based diet can give rise to the development of deficiency symptoms.

Increasing numbers of ostensibly similar products can give rise to widespread confusion. This in turn makes it more difficult for consumers to select those foodstuffs that are best suited to their individual physiological needs.

Traditions and symbolic meanings are closely associated with diet. The choice of the food we eat often sheds a light on our personal values. The consumption of plant-based alternatives is frequently associated with an urban lifestyle, whereas meat consumption tends to be linked with rural traditions. When culinary habits increasingly develop into a widespread contentious issue, this can accentuate already politically cultivated differences within society.

... And a few recommendations

Information regarding the composition of foodstuffs should be supplemented with details of essential micronutrients, and ideally should also include an indication of the burden on the environment associated with the production process. All such information should also be provided as clearly and comprehensibly as possible.

Many consumers find alternative products unpalatable if they closely resemble meat. For this reason it is important for producers of plant-based meat substitutes to ensure that the latter differ in appearance from meat products.

Plant-based alternative foodstuffs should not simply be marketed as imitations of animal-based "originals", but also as high-quality foods in their own right.

Eating habits are difficult to change

Culinary traditions are deep-rooted within a community. But scientific findings or medical recommendations can foster the demand for, and provision of, new products.

Our daily diet reflects our cultural heritage. Until and into the 19th century, for example, cheese and other dairy foods formed part of the diet in the Alps and their foothills, the prime pastures for cattle farming, whereas in the central plateau, where grain was cultivated, the population consumed a great deal of bread, and expensive hard cheese was only found on the table in affluent households.

In their turn, meat products were reserved for special occasions in Switzerland, or for people carrying out arduous physical work. Here, too, cultural heritage was a factor, at least as reported in the *Allgemeine Schweizerische Militär-Zeitung* (an official Swiss military newspaper) of 26 May 1863: "The Spanish are content with a slice of bread and an onion, especially if they are also given a cigar; the Italians prefer fruits and cheeses; and the French like their soup. (...) Our farmhands are accustomed to potatoes, full-cream milk, etc. When they join the army, they receive a daily portion of meat broth and boiled meat. All as nutritious as possible."

Practically everything available at all times

Global trade and food preservation methods ensure that practically every foodstuff is now available in Swiss supermarkets at all times. We can consume cheese and other dairy products whenever we wish, and the same applies to meat. And the availability of fruits and vegetables is no longer dependent on the season. Dairy foods and meat still account for a major portion of our diet today, but this also has its downside: the unlimited availability of foodstuffs goes hand in hand with excessive consumption and food waste.

This has consequences for the environment. In Switzerland, food consumption accounts for more than 15 percent of the average emission of CO₂ per capita. By waiving the consumption of animal-based products it would be possible to halve the level of

diet-related greenhouse gas emissions, as well as to protect biodiversity. The latter is under particular pressure, partly due to the production of meat in comparison with the manufacture of other foodstuffs.

According to Proviande (the Swiss meat industry federation), an average of almost 50 kilograms of meat was consumed per capita in Switzerland in 2022. This means that each citizen consumed around 920 grams of meat per week, which amounts to three to four times the quantity recommended by the Swiss Society for Nutrition, because excessive meat consumption is harmful to our health. Those who consume large quantities of red meat and sausage products are at higher risk of contracting diabetes, cardiovascular diseases and certain forms of cancer.

Dietary habits in transition?

Over the past 10 years, many people in Switzerland have changed their eating habits. Whereas in 2012, around 40 percent of the population waived the regular consumption of animal-based products, this figure had risen to 60 percent by 2022. Today, around 8 percent of the Swiss population exclusively consume a vegetarian diet, and roughly 0.5 percent are vegan.

For people up to the age of 29, protection of the environment is an incentive to consume less meat. People over the age of 60 tend to change their diet because of health concerns. For vegetarians and vegans the main incentive is animal welfare.

New food products on the shelves

It is possible to conjure up tasty entirely meat-free meals with beans, lentils, maize, rice and other pulses or types of grains, but traditional vegetarian foods were not the subject matter of the TA-SWISS study. Instead, the study focused on other processed foodstuffs that are intended to substitute meat and dairy products in that they are as similar as possible to them in their appearance, as well as their methods of preparation.

In the past few years, the selection of foodstuffs intended to substitute dairy products and meat has broadened. The TA-SWISS study identified a total of 378 products in Switzerland, the majority of which (209) are meat substitutes, followed by a total of 158 alternative milk and dairy products, and eleven alternative fish products.

Soya, peas and wheat are the raw materials on which around 50 percent of all the alternative foodstuffs are based. Other plants, including coconut, oats and almonds also form the basis for meat and dairy substitutes. The only non-plant-based raw material from which around 5 percent of the alternative products are created is a fungus – a mycoprotein that is used for the production of Quorn. Eggs and insects are also used as components of non-plant-based substitutes.

But are alternative products truly healthy and environment-friendly? Do consumers find them appealing? And what are their consequences for the agriculture sector? The TA-SWISS study set out to find answers to these and other questions.

Which alternative products for which “originals”?

The first step was to specify the reference products whose substitutes were to be analysed in the study.

Switzerland’s dairy industry primarily focuses on the production of cheese, butter, milk, milk powder, condensed milk, cream and yoghurt. Butter was eliminated from the study because there is an established plant-based alternative, namely margarine. Milk powder and other preserved milk products that are often used as an additive for processed foods were also excluded. Thus the focus was on alternatives to milk, cheese, cream and yoghurt.

With regard to the meat industry, pork, beef, veal and poultry account for the majority of the production. This results in eight reference products, namely each type of meat in its pure as well as its processed form as sausage products, cold meat or mincemeat for the preparation of burgers. Fish was not included in the study, because there are only very few alternative products in this category.

The following chapter deals with the alternative products for the cited foodstuffs.

The study, “Meat and dairy substitutes – better for health and the environment?”, was carried out by the Swiss agricultural research centre, Agroscope, together with the University of Bern, under the leadership of Mélanie Douziech and Eric Mehner. Otto Schäfer, a member of the Federal Ethics Committee on Non-Human Biotechnology, participated in the ethical analysis. In addition to its own analyses, the study was based on a review of the scientific literature, in-depth interviews and a quantitative online survey.

Grinding, crushing, pressing, seeding: recipes for alternative products

Alternative products should emulate original meat and dairy products as closely as possible. This places high demands on them in terms of appearance, structure and taste, and, in the best case, also nutrient content. To this end, food technology uses a broad variety of instruments and processes.

Substitutes for meat and dairy products can be divided into two main categories: products whose ingredients are grown through photosynthesis – primarily plants – can be distinguished from those whose raw materials depend on organic material or culture media. These include fungi, as well as cell cultures and insects, for which feed is required.

A further subdivision of alternative products also takes account of their degree of processing. For the production of veggie burgers or seitan – a food made from wheat protein – it is sufficient to physically process the raw material, for example by grinding and roasting it. Products such as tofu and yoghurt substitutes require more intensive treatment based on biochemical processes such as fermentation. Cell-cultivated meat, which is produced in bioreactors, and precision fermentation which uses specially designed micro-organisms, require the highest degree of processing.

Dairy products from homogenised plant-based emulsion

It is primarily plants that form the raw material for the production of milk substitutes. Soya, oats, almonds and other raw materials are initially ground and mixed with water. The solids are then eliminated through filtration and centrifugation. Finally, homogenisation is required in order to evenly distribute fat and protein particles throughout the liquid. Depending on the product, sugar, oil, aromas or other ingredients may be added to plant-based drinks.

Plant-based dairy substitutes look very similar to the “originals” made from cow’s milk, but often differ considerably from the latter in terms of nutrient content and taste.

Meat substitute from heated plant pulp

Physical methods are also used for the production of imitation meat. To produce seitan, for example, grains of wheat are crushed in a dry grinder. The meal is then mixed with water after the husks and wheat germs have been removed, and starch and gluten are subsequently separated from the resulting pulp. Finally, the extracted wheat gluten is kneaded, dried and processed into seitan, which thanks to its elastic texture can be cooked like meat.

Extrusion is a more recently introduced process. Based on the Latin term, extrudere, it refers to the process of pressing out a viscous mass through a shaping nozzle. Since the 1990s it has opened up new possibilities for the foodstuffs industry to transform globular plant protein into fibrous structures and thus emulate lean meat. Today, the majority of plant-based meat substitutes are produced through extrusion.

Broad range of culinary experiences thanks to fermentation

Fermentation is a gentle biochemical process that has been in use for centuries. It is also used for the production of meat substitutes, especially tempeh, the outward appearance of which is similar to that of camembert. It is made from peeled, boiled and fermented soya beans that have been seeded with noble mould.

The production of tofu, probably the most widely known meat substitute, is based on both physical and biochemical processes. For the production of this “vegetable quark”, soya beans are ground together with water until a smooth purée is formed, which is then filtered. Citric acid or sea-salt extract is added to the resulting soya milk – the main ingredient of tofu – so that the protein is separated from the liquid. The protein is further separated through heating, then skimmed off and pressed into blocks.

Complex processes for non-plant-based meat substitutes

Quorn has been available in supermarkets for several decades. Back in the 1960s already, British scientists discovered a rich source of protein in the *Fusarium venenatum* fungus. Following a ten-year evaluation programme, the meat substitute marketed under the brand name, Quorn, was approved by the British authorities in 1985. It was not long before this fungus-based imitation meat product was also available in Switzerland, but it remained subject to approval until the new Federal Foodstuffs Act entered into force in 2017.

Meat substitutes can also be produced from a combination of soya and insect powder, though it should be noted here that insects are also animals and thus the term “meat substitute” is not entirely accurate. The best results are obtained with a ratio of 30 to 40 percent insect protein and 60 to 70 percent soya protein. Some alternative products – especially fish substitutes – can be made on the basis of microalgae. The majority of algal strains that are currently being processed into foodstuffs are fed with sugar solution in bioreactors, because this makes them grow faster and their production is thus more efficient and less expensive.

In order to even more closely approximate the original, various companies are focusing on in-vitro cultivation of meat on the basis of cell cultures. For this purpose, a tissue sample is taken from an anaesthetised animal. To enable them to grow into meat, the few extracted cells are placed on a scaffold and fed with nutrient in a bioreactor so that they reproduce and form the desired tissue – muscle fibres or fat. Steaks produced with this process have already been presented to gastronomy experts for appraisal. Although these in-vitro steaks were found to be convincing in terms of taste, due to the high production cost – around ten times higher than that of conventional steak – they are unlikely to make a breakthrough onto the mass market in the foreseeable future.

Innovations in the pipeline

The plant-based beverages currently available in supermarkets are made from various types of grains and from soya. But the potato is also a promising candidate for alternative dairy products. A Swedish start-up recently brought a potato-based beverage onto the market.

The foodstuffs industry is not only looking for new raw materials, but is also focusing on the utilisation of residual materials. For the production of an imitation meat, a start-up in the canton of Bern is using okara (soya bean pulp), which is left over following the production of tofu and soya milk. In Switzerland alone, around 2,000 tonnes of this high-nutrient pulp is produced, and currently most of it ends up in biogas plants. The company concerned refines a mixture of fermented okara and chickpeas into what it calls an “ideal additive for creative dishes of all kinds”.

Various innovative moulding processes are enriching the range of products. In an extrusion process a French company is combining “lean meat” produced from soya extract with fat from sunflower oil, and forming the mixture into visually attractive “bacon” strips that are subsequently smoked with beech wood to enhance their taste. For the production of an imitation steak, a team from the Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich is also applying an extrusion process using two nozzles. Thanks to specially developed software, the utilised pea protein, which emulates muscle fibres, randomly combines with the fat and thus creates the marbling pattern that is characteristic of steak.

It is also conceivable that 3-D printing could be used for producing imitation meat in the future. However, this technology is not yet sufficiently advanced for use on an industrial scale.

Lucrative prospects for alternative meat and dairy products

Substitutes only account for a very small proportion of the overall range of meat and dairy products. The growth potential for alternative products is therefore considerable.

The range of plant-based substitutes for meat and dairy products is not only constantly expanding in Switzerland: in 2020, the amount invested in the development of alternative products worldwide increased by a factor of three versus 2019. And just one year later, investment had increased by a factor of five versus 2019 to reach five billion US dollars. In North and Latin America, the Asia Pacific region and Europe, investment in the development of innovative foodstuffs is especially high. The TA-SWISS study identified a total of 107 start-ups that are looking for potential meat substitutes. The majority of these companies are domiciled in the USA, followed by Israel and the UK.

Switzerland a significant producer of dairy substitutes

Around half the alternative products available in Swiss shops originate from here, EU countries and the UK. Most of the dairy substitutes are produced in Switzerland, while the majority of imitation meats are imported from the EU.

Coop is the only major Swiss retailer that reports sales figures concerning alternative products and their share of the overall product range. In 2023, vegan burgers accounted for one-fifth of its overall

sales of burgers. In its cold meats department, alternative products accounted for 14 percent of its total sales in this product category.

In 2022, its sales of plant-based alternatives for dairy products amounted to 126.7 million Swiss francs, followed by plant-based meat substitutes (88.1 million). But these figures should not detract from the fact that the market share of meat and dairy substitutes is still very low: in 2021, plant-based meat substitutes accounted for barely 2.3 percent, and plant-based dairy substitutes for around 3.3 percent, of the respective total markets for meat and dairy products. Thus in the view of the providers, there is strong growth potential. In the period from 2016 to 2022 alone, the average annual growth rate for alternative meat products was 18.4 percent. According to specialists, the share of alternative products will continue to grow worldwide in the future. For imitation meats they predict a market share of up to 60 percent in 2040.

Low demand for insect-based products

Some insect species were approved as foodstuffs in Switzerland in 2017. Demand for insect-based products has stagnated at the very low level of 0.005 percent of the overall meat market, including alternative products that contain insects as well as other components. Sales of alternative products enriched with insects peaked in 2019 at 420,000 Swiss francs. One year later this figure fell by one-third. Swiss retail chain Migros consequently removed edible insects from its product range, while Coop retained selected items such as a protein bar and a meal-worm burger.

Nutrients that improve our health

A balanced and varied diet is beneficial to our health. If we vary our diet, we increase our chances of absorbing all the necessary nutrients.

Dietary fibres such as those found in vegetables and fruits contain almost no calories, but they stimulate intestinal activity and strengthen our immune system. They also ensure that we feel satiated for a longer period of time, and thus help prevent obesity. Proteins are one of the components of living organisms. Among other things, they form muscle and supporting tissue. Calcium, which in terms of volume is the most important mineral in our body, is essential for the strength and durability of our bones and teeth. Iron is involved in numerous processes in our body, especially the transport of oxygen in the blood. Iodine is a component of the thyroid hormone, thyroxin, which regulates cardiac activity, blood pressure and body temperature. Finally, vitamin B12, which is found exclusively in animal-based foodstuffs, is involved in various metabolic processes and plays an important role with regard to blood formation.

But there are also some nutrients that we should treat with caution. Reticence is advisable with respect to the consumption of sugar, salt and saturated fatty acids. Sugar subjects the body to stress and in the long term can cause insulin resistance and thus diabetes. Salt can cause high blood pressure and increase the risk of cardiovascular diseases, while saturated fatty acids increase the level of “bad” cholesterol, which can also cause cardiovascular problems.

In the TA-SWISS study, the nutrient content of the various alternative products was compared with that of the respective animal-based “originals”.

Desirable and undesirable content

Given their plant-based origin it is no surprise that alternatives for meat and dairy products are characterised by a high proportion of dietary fibres and in this regard significantly surpass foodstuffs from animal sources. The iron content in plant-based substitutes is also higher than in meat and dairy products. However, it is more difficult for the human organism to absorb iron from plants than from meat.

By contrast, cow’s milk, yoghurt and cheese have a higher calcium and iodine content than their alternative products. In its turn, unprocessed pork stands out for its high protein and vitamin B12 content. But if it is processed into sausage products or cold meat, the disqualifying and thus undesirable nutrients such as salt and saturated fatty acids predominate and consequently offset the health benefit.

If we observe the variants within the product groups, significant discrepancies become apparent. For example, the calcium content of oat, almond and soya milk fluctuates by up to a factor of 13, which gives rise to the assumption that calcium is added to some products. By comparison, the calcium content of cow’s milk is relatively constant. In terms of protein content, soya milk comes closest to cow’s milk, whereas the level in other milk substitutes is much lower. On the other hand, the fact that the proportion of unsaturated fatty acids in plant-based beverages is higher than in cow’s milk is one of their health benefits.

It’s the combination that counts

One of the principles frequently cited in cookery books from bygone eras also applies to the various alternative products: it’s the combination that counts, not the individual ingredients. For example, a high content of dietary fibres can slow down or inhibit the digestion of other nutrients. Plant-based foodstuffs also often contain cell structures that interfere with the digestive process. The way in which alternative products are prepared is a decisive factor here: fermentation is especially beneficial in that it helps improve the bioavailability of plant-based ingredients.

Amino acids, i.e. the chemical components of proteins, are essential for us, and in terms of their composition, those from animal-based products meet the requirements of our organism better than those from plants. Through a suitable combination of the plant-based foods we consume we can increase the intake of all the amino acids we require for our nutrition: a combination of rice and peas is a good example, and a combination of peas, rapeseed and potatoes is even better.

Ready-to-serve pizzas and other highly processed foods have a high content of salt, sugar, saturated fatty acids and preservatives. And many substitutes for meat and dairy products also have to be classified as highly processed foodstuffs. These often contain high levels of sugar and fat, though in most cases the content of the latter is barely higher than that of animal-based reference products. The TA-SWISS study also shows that ostensibly similar alternative products can greatly differ in terms of their composition. Consumers thus have the possibility to choose a high-quality plant-based schnitzel, as long as they are able to grasp and correctly classify the numerous product specifications.

The way in which meat and dairy substitutes are prepared in the kitchen also plays a role. Fat-soluble vitamins A, D, E and K can only be optimally absorbed in combination with a certain amount of fat, whereas vitamins in the B and C complex are water-soluble and easily washed out. Generally speaking, heat destroys vitamins. So whether we fry a plant-based schnitzel in hot oil or prepare it in a steamer can potentially determine which substances we ingest.

Attention to individual needs

Within the population there are groups whose needs vary in terms of specific nutrients. Adolescents, for example, need a high level of calcium, while women often have too little iron in their blood due to menstruation. The need for macronutrients and energy – i.e. carbohydrates and fat – is higher in men than in women, whereas the need for energy decreases with age, but not for vitamins and minerals.

Depending on the nutrient that may be deficient, the consumption of alternative meat or dairy products can have both a positive and a negative effect on a person's health. Here attention has to be paid to individual needs – especially with regard to how much the food we ingest depends on both the composition of a product and its preparation. Many influencing factors interact here, so that it is not possible to make a generalised assessment of the effects on our health of, for example, a veggie burger or a potato-based beverage.

Consequences for the foodstuffs industry and the environment

In many countries, wheat, maize, rice and soya are staple foods. In Switzerland, we import large quantities of these products as concentrated feed so that our cattle put on more meat and produce more milk.

Land use and water consumption, greenhouse gas emissions, plus the threat of acidification or over-fertilisation of the soil, are all consequences associated with the production of foodstuffs. So how do plant-based meat and beverages perform in comparison with the reference products of animal origin?

Higher water consumption and lower CO₂ emissions

If fewer animals are kept on farms and more plants are cultivated instead, this tends to have a positive impact on the environment. In Finland, for example, it has been demonstrated that a reduction in the consumption of meat greatly reduces both land use and greenhouse gas emissions. Furthermore, the freed-up land can be used for reforestation, and this facilitates the additional storage of CO₂.

When we enter into more detail, it is clear that plant-based alternatives are in many ways better for the environment in comparison with pork chops and cow's milk. There are some exceptions, however: for the production of plant-based beverages, yoghurt and cream substitutes, the water requirement is significantly higher than for the animal-based reference products. In the case of oat and almond beverages, the levels of water consumption are four, respectively 30 times higher in comparison with cow's milk. With regard to imitation meats, only those products made on the basis of cell cultures perform poorly compared with animal-based products.

Apart from these exceptions, products such as wheat- or soya-based schnitzel stand out in terms of their average greenhouse gas potential, which is around six times lower than that of meat. And the greenhouse gas potential for the production of falafel is even 15 times lower. Falafel and soya-based products thus have the lowest impact on the environment of all the examined products.

If the findings are translated to proteins, and thus to a significant parameter for determining the quality of foodstuffs, then the environmental impacts attributable to alternative products are still lower than those of the reference products, even though the latter are now making up ground thanks to their high protein content. Due to their comparatively low protein content, when analysed in this way, falafel and tempeh in particular indicate higher environmental impact levels than in absolute terms.

Plant cultivation increases the degree of self-sufficiency

In Switzerland, meat and dairy products account for a large proportion of the turnover of the agriculture sector (55 percent). In these two categories, Switzerland's degree of self-sufficiency is high: in 2022, the level was 94 percent for milk and more than 100 percent for cheese, and the figures for veal (96 percent) and beef (84 percent) were also high. By way of comparison, with respect to poultry, the degree of self-sufficiency is 59 percent.

A differentiated assessment makes sense, because poultry and pigs need concentrated feed, which means they compete with human beings for food, whereas cattle essentially could feed solely on grass. The role played by cattle in Switzerland is all the more important in that pastures and meadows account for 70 percent of the land that is at all suitable for agricultural use. The raw fodder that grows there – grass in the summer, hay for the winter – can only be consumed by ruminants, i.e. cattle, goats, sheep, and equine species (horses and donkeys). This means that dairy production and the production of veal and beef do not necessarily compete with the production of foodstuffs for the population. But because cattle often need supplementary concentrated feed, if they were only able to feed on grass and hay the yield of meat as well as milk would be lower. As before, numerous cows could graze in fields and pastures: according to a model calculation of the Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW), if concentrated feed were to no longer be provided, it would still be possible to retain 85 percent of the current stock of cattle.

Switzerland imports more than 50 percent of the quantities of soya and grains fed to cattle. Nonetheless, cattle fodder is currently cultivated on around 41 percent of open farmland here, and this land could be used for the cultivation of potatoes, onions and other vegetables. The soil properties and climate in Switzerland would also be suitable for the cultivation of various pulses such as soya, broad beans or lupines. As a variety of calculations show, with the cultivation of pulses it would be possible to produce at least as large a quantity of protein as the Swiss population currently consumes in the form of meat.

Diverse landscape as an asset

If we were to entirely discontinue livestock farming, would it be the environment that would stand to benefit the most? Quite apart from the fact that the mosaic of open landscapes, meadows and forests is a distinctive feature of rural Switzerland and forms an integral part of its tourism capital, the consequences for the environment would also not only be positive.

If no more cattle were to graze in the pastures, this would give rise to a proliferation of bushes and shrubs, and later on trees. While certain types of bushes can foster biodiversity, this would be drastically reversed if large areas of grassland were to become completely overgrown with trees and shrubs. This could lead to a reduction in the diversity of species by more than 50 percent in comparison with open grassland. A strong proliferation of green alder (the most common bush in the Alps) would have a particularly negative impact. In a symbiotic relationship with certain bacteria, green alder absorbs nitrogen from the air and thus transfers it to the soil. The consequences are the same as those of mineral fertilisation: species that depend on poor soil disappear.

Price, availability, appearance: social status of alternative products

Whether certain goods are readily available to consumers and how much they cost influences their social and economic sustainability. And whether they are of appeal to consumers also plays a role.

High-quality meals can be expensive. The price and availability of foodstuffs are significant influencing factors for their social and economic sustainability. The TA-SWISS study found that the average price for plant-based beverages is up to four times higher than that of cow's milk. This is consistent with the findings cited in the scientific literature, according to which the price for school meals increases sharply if soya drinks are provided as a substitute for cow's milk. For meat substitutes the price difference is less pronounced, because numerous plant-based products cost less than the animal-based "originals".

Willingness to pay, i.e. the price a consumer is prepared to pay for something, is regarded as an indicator for the social status of a given product. The willingness to pay more for alternative products appears to be high, at least in the case of relatively inexpensive products such as milk. However, the findings of various studies show that the willingness to pay for alternative meat products is often lower than that for comparable animal-based products – evidence of the status attached to meat by many consumers.

Assessment and consumption of alternative products

Who decides to try alternative products? Who buys them how often, and why? The TA-SWISS study carried out a quantitative and qualitative survey in order to find answers to these questions.

In the quantitative online survey, 87 percent of the 1,034 respondents between the ages of 18 and 74 (of whom 20 percent are flexitarian and 6 percent have a vegetarian or vegan diet) stated that they had tried a plant-based alternative meat or dairy product at least once. However, trying such products once does not necessarily lead to their regular consumption: more than 40 percent of the respondents who tried an alternative product once rarely or never consume it. Fewer than one-third regularly (at least

once a week) consume alternative dairy or meat products. A large proportion of the respondents stated that they never want to consume any of the 15 alternative products listed in the questionnaire. The most strongly rejected products are insect balls, plant-based sausages and non-dairy cheeses.

A significantly larger number of respondents are prepared to substitute meat than dairy products. More than half see no necessity to reduce their consumption of milk. With respect to meat, however, more than two-thirds are of the opinion that its consumption should be reduced. Around 45 percent of the respondents say they have already reduced their consumption of meat, while only around 25 percent consume less dairy products.

With respect to the effects on health and the environmental impacts of various alternative products, the responses are inconclusive. It appears that many people find it difficult to assess the ecological sustainability of a given product. And the respondents also have difficulty in assessing the effects of alternative products on health.

Differing attitudes, other preferences

The findings of the qualitative survey that was carried out in the form of in-depth interviews show that significant differences exist among the present-day Swiss population with respect to dietary habits and preferences. This also depends on whether people want plant-based substitutes to be as similar in appearance as possible to the respective animal-based "originals".

For those who prefer their meals to include meat (designated as "conservative meat consumers" in the study), it is culinary pleasure that takes precedence. In their view, a departure from traditional dietary habits is unnecessary, and there are no grounds for replacing something they find so tasty. They are opposed to the use of alternative products; many of them find a strong similarity between meat and plant-based imitation products off-putting, and some even consider them to be a form of deception.

Another group (referred to as "progressive meat consumers") comprises people who like to eat meat

but are also convinced that the food system needs to change. In their view, food technology offers intriguing solutions that they are prepared to give a try. The greater the similarity between plant-based alternatives and the corresponding animal-based products the better, and they prefer not to have to adapt their own eating habits more than necessary. Thus, for the respondents in this group, meat consumption can be reduced without having to make a major sacrifice.

Those who pragmatically eat foods that taste good, but for whom meat is not as important as it is for the members of the above groups, decide on a case-by-case basis whether to choose a pork chop or an alternative product (“undogmatic omnivores”). Here the choice often depends on factors such as availability or price. Whether an alternative product resembles meat is of secondary importance.

People in the fourth group (“mainly vegetarian”) primarily consume plant-based products and are in favour of a change in the food system. They prefer products that do not appear too similar to meat and whose plant-based origin is still visible. Some even find products repellent if they too closely resemble meat.

Generally speaking, the findings from the two surveys indicate that for the majority of the participants it is a positive taste experience that is the determining factor for the choice of foodstuffs. Aspects such as health also play a role, as does – to a lesser extent – ecological sustainability. It is also interesting to note that alternatives for dairy products are socially more acceptable than meat substitutes, whereas in the context of ecological impacts and health effects, it is the use of alternative dairy products that are viewed more critically than meat substitutes.

Deception prevention and animal welfare: legal and ethical principles

Legal experts already focused on the importance attached to animal welfare at an early stage. Swiss food legislation calls for the use of labels that ensure the precise identification of food products.

The provisions of the Federal Foodstuffs and Consumer Goods Act are intended to protect the health of consumers, prevent deceptions and provide information consumers need in order to purchase foodstuffs. Detailed explanatory information regarding the implementation of the Act is provided in more than thirty supplementary directives.

Alternative meat and dairy products are not governed by any specific regulations. Since the revision of the Act was completed in 2017, these products may be distributed and sold as long as they meet the same requirements such as hygienic production and handling, traceability, labelling, etc., that apply to all other foodstuffs.

Article 19 of the Act stipulates, that alternative products must be clearly labelled so that it is possible for consumers to identify the true nature of the foodstuff and distinguish it from products for which it could be mistaken. Various products such as milk, mayonnaise and butter are precisely defined by law so that their designation cannot be applied to plant-based alternatives. For this reason, shops in Switzerland do not sell soya or oat “milk”, but rather “drinks”.

The prevention of deception is currently the focus of attention in ongoing legal cases concerning alternative products. After the administrative court of Zurich had ruled in autumn 2022 that a start-up called Planted Foods AG could market its products under the designation, “planted chicken”, the Federal Department of Home Affairs lodged an appeal at the Federal Supreme Court against the ruling. The case is still pending, and it could result in a tightening up of the provisions governing the prevention of deception.

In a communiqué the Federal Administration declared that inventive neologisms such as “veganise”, “mylk” or “vromage” are not admissible as designations for alternative products. In 2020 the German Federal Patent Court rejected the registration of “vromage” as a product name because it

obscures the distinction between the products and thus increases the risk of deception.

The specialists in the field of foodstuff legislation who were interviewed within the framework of the TA-SWISS study generally agree that there is no special need for amendments to the legal provisions that apply to alternative products. In order to support innovation, it would be helpful, according to the interviewees, if the procedures governing the approval of alternative products could be implemented more quickly.

Capacity for suffering outweighs reason

The first philosophers who spoke out against the practice of killing animals for food were the proponents of utilitarianism – representatives of an ethic that is based on the outcome of an action and then regards it as acceptable if it aims to maximise the well-being for all concerned. Jeremy Bentham, an English lawyer and political reformer, is regarded as the founder of utilitarianism. In his work, “An Introduction to the Principles of Morals and Legislation” (published in 1870), he complained that in the past, jurists had neglected animals in their deliberations and downgraded them to objects. He declared that the way in which animals have to be treated does not depend on whether they are able to think or speak. Here it is the capacity for suffering that is the decisive factor. Present-day proponents of animal ethics such as Peter Singer also base their argumentation on the criterion of capacity for suffering. In their view, our enjoyment of the consumption of meat does not outweigh, or even justify, the animals’ suffering due to the adverse conditions under which they are kept and subsequently slaughtered.

Utilitarianism is not the only possible ethical approach for assessing alternative products. All approaches have one thing in common, namely that they are embedded in the specific living conditions. They have to balance norms and goods against each other that contradict one another: one such contradiction would be between the enjoyment of the individual to consume meat and an officially decreed consumption of alternative products. Personal responsibility and freedom are also ethically relevant values.

Environment, animal welfare and naturalness

In addition to a comprehensive analysis of the philosophical literature, interviews with three ethicists were conducted for the TA-SWISS study.

With respect to the environmental-ethical assessment of the alternative products, all three agree: in view of the high level of greenhouse gas emissions and other ecological consequences associated with meat production, the performance of the alternative products is better than that of the animal-based reference products.

Animal welfare is also a strong argument that speaks in favour of the alternative products. Killing animals for food is wrong – although in the view of one of the interviewed specialists it is not the consumers who act in a morally questionable way, but rather the meat industry. Furthermore, it is important to observe the dignity of living beings as laid down in the Swiss Federal Constitution. This is compromised through excessive instrumentalisation, for example the breeding or modification of animals with heritable defects, resulting in their suffering. In the field of agricultural livestock, this applies for example to certain types of turkey that, for the sake of maximising profits, are bred to gain weight so rapidly that their legs are no longer able to support their bodyweight.

In the opinion of the interviewees, the allocation of insect powder to the field of alternative meat production is also questionable. Although the applicable legislation differentiates between vertebrates and invertebrates (which includes insects), but the principle of dignity of living beings defined in the Swiss Federal Constitution applies without restriction. If we attempt to quantify animal welfare, the situation for insects is especially unfavourable: although individually they suffer the least in comparison with all other creatures, because they are tiny and thus a large quantity of them is required for the production of a foodstuff, they have the highest cumulative suffering per product unit.

By contrast, the argument of naturalness asserted by consumers is not valid from an ethical perspective. What nature is, does not determine what a human being should do. Or to put it another way, no ethical imperative can be deduced from the description of the world alone.

Tradition also has its place

The interviewed ethicists differentiate their rejection of meat and milk consumption from an everyday perspective. They point out that our culture is traditionally one of meat consumption, which tends to be associated with strength and masculinity. In addition, social standing is another value. Many farm workers suffer from a lack of appreciation for their activities, and recognition is also associated with cooking and eating. The degree of recognition is considerably lessened with the widespread use of ready-to-cook pre-prepared plant-based alternative products.

In this context the interviewed ethicists fear there could be a division of society in that the consumption of substitute meat and dairy products would be accepted in an urban environment, but rejected in primarily rural areas.

Focus on own strengths

The authors of the study come to the conclusion that there is still too strong a focus on traditions relating to the consumption of animal-based foodstuffs. As long as this remains the case, it will be difficult for alternative products to gain ground, because as “imitations” they are hardly ever able to approximate the taste and other sensorial features of the “originals”. For the time being it may make sense to endeavour to achieve a resemblance between substitutes and their reference products in order to encourage their acceptance on the part of consumers. In the long term, however, a too strong resemblance with meat and dairy products could in fact have a negative effect in terms of drawing attention to the beneficial properties of substitutes. It is likely that the products examined in the study still have quite a long way to go before their status can be changed from “imitations” to “second degree originals” that are accepted as such in view of their specific properties.

Thus, the introduction of a new tradition of protein plants in Switzerland would be auspicious: why should Swiss chickpeas or Swiss lupine not be able to attain a similar symbolic status over time to that of the Swiss cow – especially in view of the fact that foodstuffs are being marketed today with an increasing focus on the quality of proteins rather than their animal origin? Here, pulses could play a larger role.

Urgent recommendation for maximum transparency

When we shop for foodstuffs, it is by no means easy to evaluate processed products. The small print on labels offers little help in assessing the health and ecological benefits of a given product. Transparency is therefore of the utmost importance in order to make the right purchase decision.

Alternative products perform well from both an ethical and an ecological perspective. But in accordance with the findings of the study there is a need for a certain degree of differentiation regarding their nutritional value.

Meat substitutes more recommendable than alternative dairy products

The consumption of meat substitutes can be recommended, with certain reservations. However, some nutrients are more difficult for the human organism to process than those that are found in animal-based products – this primarily applies to iron and zinc. Vitamin B12 is another critical nutrient that only occurs naturally in animal-based products. In an exclusively plant-based diet, a deficit of vitamin B5, iodine and proteins cannot be ruled out.

On the other hand, substituting dairy products can only be conditionally recommended. Here the necessary high level of water consumption is a burden on the environment. In addition, with the exception of soya drinks, the performance of alternative products is poorer than that of the reference products in terms of content of proteins and calcium, unless these are incorporated as additives.

Comprehensible and detailed product information is essential

In order for consumers to be able to choose an alternative product that meets their physiological needs, values and demands, the provision of detailed and comprehensible information is essential. Information provided on product labels should be supplemented with details concerning the nutrition content (including iron and calcium) and bioavailability. In addition, information should be provided regarding the environmental burdens associated with the product.

People at risk of malnourishment should pay special attention to the content of those nutrients that are of special importance for them.

Need for a creative foodstuffs industry

When alternative products are made to resemble the reference products (especially meat) this is by no means appreciated by all consumers. In order to meet the differing demands of consumers, alternative meat products should be available that are marketed less on the basis of imitation and more on the substitution of nutrients.

Nutrition is closely associated with traditions, role models and other symbolic dimensions. By primarily designing substitutes as meat and dairy product imitations, they are assigned a comparatively low value. The foodstuffs industry therefore needs to find a way to elevate alternative products to the status of valued components within Switzerland's dietary culture.

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